

Total Fe content in the leaves of tolerant and susceptible lines was unrelated to deficiency symptoms (Table 2). However, orthophenanthroline reactive Fe²⁺ content of the leaves appeared to be related with deficiency symptoms. Lines with less than 30 ppm orthophenanthroline reactive Fe²⁺ in the upper leaves were more susceptible than those with 30 to 40 ppm Fe²⁺. Lines with more than 40 ppm Fe²⁺ were tolerant.

Dry matter accumulation was significantly and positively correlated with orthophenanthroline reactive Fe²⁺ ($r = 0.90^{**}$). □

Table 2. Total dry matter content, Fe, and orthophenanthroline reactive Fe²⁺ in upper leaves of rice genotypes, Samastipur, India.

Entry	Dry matter yield (g/20 plants)	Total Fe (ppm)	Orthophenanthroline Fe ²⁺ (ppm)
IET7973	6.7	240	50
IET7972	6.3	255	42
IET5882	6.0	260	37
Pankaj	3.4	375	33
IET6263	5.2	450	36
Pusa 33	3.1	490	32
Mahsuri	2.6	337	28
Saket 4	2.7	288	30
T141	3.6	500	33

Pest control and management DISEASES

Effect of planting date on rice tungro virus (RTV) infection

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In 1980 wet season RTV infection increased in north and south Bihar. At the Pusa Experimental Farm, RTV developed the first week of Aug and attained maximum severity in Sep. In a yield evaluation trial with 16 entries planted at 3 dates, RTV infection developed at different times.

The entries were planted in a randomized block on 25 May, 9 Jun, and 24 Jun 1980 and 30-d-old seedlings were transplanted in 20- × 15-cm spacing in 7.5-m²

plots. NPK was applied at 80, 40, and 20 kg/ha. PK was applied basally and N was applied in three splits. The maximum score from three replications was used to classify entries for RTV reaction (see table). Green leafhopper population was high.

Only RP967-11-1-4-2-2 was infected on the first planting date, but many other entries developed RTV when planted on the second and third dates. Pusa 33, Pusa 2-21, Saket 4, and Ratna were resistant. Rajendra Dhan 201 and IET5656 had intermediate resistance.

The recorded infection rate show that agronomic manipulations such as early planting can minimize RTV infection in susceptible cultivars. Plant age and varying incubation period also may affect disease development. □

RTV infection of varieties planted at different dates at Pusa, India.

Entry	RTV reaction ^a		
	25 May	9 Jun	24 Jun
Pusa 33	1	1	1
Pusa 2-21	1	1	1
Govind (UPR82-1-7)	1	1	7
Saket 4 (CR44-35)	1	1	1
Ratna	1	1	1
Prasad	1	7	9
Jaya	1	7	9
IR8	1	7	9
Sita	1	7	9
Rajendra Dhan 201	1	1	5
BG90-2	1	9	9
SPR7284-57-5	1	1	9
RP967-11-1-4-2-2	7	7	9
Pankaj	1	1	7
RP975-109-2 (IET5656)	1	1	5
MRI	1	7	9

^aBy the 0-9 scale of the 1980 Standard Evaluation System for Rice.

A new rice virus disease in India

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In late samba 1983, many rice varieties with yellow-orange leaves were observed in farmer fields and at the University of Coimbatore. Only a few plants showed symptoms that resembled those of rice

tungro virus (RTV). Plants had mild stunting and increased tillering. Brown planthopper (BPH) was in the fields. Infected plants were collected and transmission tests were conducted by using the green leafhopper (GLH) *Nephotettix virescens* Dist. and BPH *Nilaparvata lugens* Stål.

Virus-free GLH adults given 4-d acquisition access feeding on source plants were transferred to 10-d-old TN1

seedlings at 2 insects/seedling for 4-d inoculation access. The inoculated plants did not develop disease symptoms (Table 1).

Second-instar nymphs from a virus-free BPH colony were released on source plants for 7-d acquisition access feeding, and then collected and released on 10-d-old TN1 seedlings at 2 insects/plant for 10-d inoculation access feeding. The inoculated plants developed yellow-